

Transformative agreements in Austria: Cost sharing challenges

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15 SEPTEMBER 2020, OPEN ACCESS TAGE

Austrian Academic Library Consortium (KEMÖ)

THE CONSORTIUM IN AUSTRIA

58 members:

- universities – public and private
- universities of applied sciences
- other institutions: ex.: research institutes, Academy of Sciences etc.
- Austrian Science Fund, cOAlition S member

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Plan S
Making full and immediate Open Access a reality

FUNDING & TYPES OF AGREEMENTS

- **Bottom-up** organisation
- **No central funding** available
- Everything comes from **institutional budgets**
- **Opt-in** agreements
- **OA-deal** negotiated wherever possible

Consortial OA publishing agreements

Share of articles in Plan S-ready venues

Articles in Plan S – ready venues* among AT2OA project partners

- 🔒 49% in transformative agreements
- 🔒 22% in DOAJ journals
- 🔒 Authors have the option to publish OA in all these venues

Articles in subscription journals, no agreement:

- 🔒 3% of articles in journals that are excluded from the various transformative agreements
- 🔒 26 % long tail of publishers

- 🔒🔒 Articles can still be compliant in other ways („repository route“)

*Source: 2018 bibliographic data from WoS and Scopus by AT2OA, and 2020 transformative agreements

Money, money, money

The greatest challenge we have been trying to tackle here in Austria:

- **Financing transformative agreements**

Part of the solution:

- **„cost neutral agreements“** with publishers

But what exactly do we mean by „cost neutrality“?

Based on historic spend:

licence fees + APCs to date + moderate increase = cost neutral agreement

More on cost neutral agreements

Austrian Transition to Open Access project

AT2OA <https://at2oa.at/en/home.html>

2017-2020 and 2021 -2024

- Led and hosted by the University of Vienna
- Project deliverables:
 - supporting the large-scale transformation of scientific publications from closed to OA &
 - to implement measure supporting this goal

Aim of Subproject 2:

funding for transitional Open Access business models. Agreements partially funded:

- Springer Compact 2017-2019
- Wiley 2018-2020

Springer Compact 2019-2021 – new cost distribution model

Basis for the model:

- 2016-2018 publishing patterns
- Market value of APCs vs subscription spend
- Gradual move towards a more publishing-output based model

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Tiers 1 to 4

- Different annual increases applied to previous spend
- Lowest in Tier 1, highest in Tier 4
- Increase must **remain under 10%** per annum
- Reason: must be a **gradual change**

Analysis: members spend vs APC market value in 2016 - 2018

Reactions from members – how well is the model working?

- Not a top down model!
- Developed *by* and *for* the Consortium
- **Gradual changes** so that the increase in costs is not as acutely felt

- **Challenging for Tiers 3 and 4**, to sign up to the new model but everyone agreed in the end
- **Transitional model**
- **Not possible to move in one go** from subscription-based spend to a purely publication output-based model

Thank you!

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More about our experience:

On Plan S

Pinhasi, Kromp, Blechl, Hölbling.
2020. **“The impact of Open Access publishing agreements at the University of Vienna in light of the Plan S requirements: a review of current status, challenges and perspectives”**. *Insights*. DOI <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.523> (article in press, DOI not yet active, to be published in Nov. 2020)

On workflows

Pinhasi, Blechl, Kromp, Schubert.
2018. **“The Weakest Link – Workflows in Open Access Agreements: The Experience of the Vienna University Library and Recommendations for Future Negotiations”**. *Insights* 31: 27. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.419>